

Carotenoid production by *Haloferax mediterranei* using starch residues from the candy industry as a carbon source

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ABSTRACT

Carotenoids are pigments attracting the attention of several industries due to their antioxidant, biological and coloring properties. Low-cost substrates, such as agro-industrial wastes, are being investigated as a viable option to reduce microbial production costs in processes in which microorganisms such as haloarchaea are used as cell factories to produce marketed compounds like carotenoids. They can grow on various agro-industrial wastes and produce the C₅₀ carotenoid bacterioruberin (BR), which is an extraordinary antioxidant compound with anti-cancer properties. In this study, the haloarchaeon *Haloferax mediterranei* is grown in the presence of starch residues from the candy industry to induce the production of carotenoids. Cells grew successfully with this industrial waste (max. O.D. 600 nm = 27.75 ± 0.09). Biomass production increased in the presence of higher quantities of starch up to 17.3 ± 0.2 mg/ml of cell culture. The maximum BR concentration was 97.39 ± 1.86 µg/ml. The total amount of BRs synthesized increased when cells grew with increasing concentrations of the industrial starch. The relative percentages of all-*trans*-BR, 5-*cis*-BR and a double isomeric BR rose, whereas 9-*cis*-BR and 13-*cis*-BR levels decreased.

Herein, haloarchaeal growth and carotenoid production can be enhanced using industrial waste products as the starch residues selected for this experiment which were provided by a candy company.

1. Introduction

Carotenoids have garnered significant attention from various industries, including pharmaceutical, biomedical, chemical, food, and cosmetics due to their antioxidant and colouring properties (Giani et al., 2021b; Milani et al., 2017; Rao and Rao, 2007; Rodríguez-Concepción et al., 2018). The production of carotenoids by traditional methods like chemical synthesis has faced challenges such as high production costs, negative environmental impact due to the organic solvents and reactive used during their synthesis and reduced customer acceptance (which currently prefer natural carotenoids). The prevalent utilization of synthetic carotenoids in the last decades has sparked deliberations among the global scientific community and international health organizations, regarding the potential long-term consequences that these substances might exert on human well-being (Mussagy et al., 2019). As a result, synthetic carotenoids are being substituted in many products and, efforts are being directed towards researching and developing highly

stable and functional natural pigments (Zaccarim et al., 2019). Consequently, there has been a growing interest in exploring alternative approaches, and microbial production of natural carotenoids has emerged as a promising solution. A key advantage of microbial production is its cost-effectiveness due to the use of low-cost substrates like agro-industrial wastes to make carotenoid production more economically viable and sustainable (Henke et al., 2018; Mata-Gómez et al., 2014; Mussagy et al., 2019; Rodrigo-Baños et al., 2015).

Haloarchaea are extremophilic microorganisms that thrive in hypersaline environments and show remarkable potential in carotenoid production (Oren, 2015), reaching values up to 556 mg/L (Will Chen et al., 2015). These microorganisms show impressive growth capabilities on diverse agro-industrial wastes and can produce substantial amounts of the rare C₅₀ carotenoid known as bacterioruberin (Giani et al., 2019; Oren, 2020). Haloarchaea utilize C₅₀ carotenoids as a defence mechanism against osmotic stress and radiation in their hypersaline habitats (Jones and Baxter, 2017). Haloarchaeal cell cultures, particularly due to

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their high salt concentration, offer a lower risk of contamination, eliminating the need for sterilization. Moreover, cell lysis can be easily achieved by exposing them to a hypotonic solution, also reducing production costs compared to other mechanisms used for cell lysis (sonication, French press, etc.) (Montero-Lobato et al., 2018). All these facts are advantages of the use of haloarchaea as cell factories to produce carotenoids versus their bacterial or yeast counterparts.

Bacterioruberin (BR) and its derivatives, monoanhydrobacterioruberin (MABR) and bisanhydrobacterioruberin (BABR) are the main components found in haloarchaeal carotenoid extracts (Bidle et al., 2007; Kelly et al., 1967). BR is distinguished by a primary isoprenoid chain containing thirteen conjugated double bonds and four hydroxyl groups in the terminal ends, making it exceptionally rich in antioxidant properties compared to C₄₀ and C₃₀ carotenoids like β -carotene and staphyloxanthin (Giani et al., 2022; Torregrosa-Crespo et al., 2017). This makes BR highly valuable for various biomedical applications, including cancer treatment (Giani et al., 2023; Hegazy et al., 2020; Shahbazi et al., 2023), antiviral potential (Hegazy et al., 2020), and sperm motility improvement (Zalazar et al., 2019). *Haloflex mediterranei* stands out among haloarchaea for its versatile carbon source consumption and extensive research on its metabolism (Bhattacharyya et al., 2014; Giani et al., 2021a; Huang et al., 2006; Quillaguamán et al., 2010; Torregrosa-Crespo et al., 2016). It has proven useful in producing bioplastics like polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) (Cánovas et al., 2021; Koller et al., 2017; Simó-Cabrera et al., 2021) and serves as a model microorganism in various fields, including the study of biogeochemical cycles like nitrogen cycle (Torregrosa-Crespo et al., 2020) or the bioremediation of salty wastewaters (Nájera-Fernández et al., 2012; Saez-Zamacona et al., 2023).

Carotenoids are traditionally sourced from resource-intensive practices (Vachali et al., 2012). By harnessing the capability of haloarchaea to produce carotenoids in controlled environments, circular economy projects can reduce reliance on chemical synthesis and plant production, minimizing costs, the release of toxic wastes and land and water usage, respectively (Rodrigo-Baños et al., 2015). The closed-loop nature of these projects ensures efficient nutrient recycling and waste utilization, aligning with circular economy principles. This innovative approach not only conserves resources but also contributes to a more sustainable and resilient bio-based economy. The use of industrial residues as nutrient sources has been evaluated in many microbial species, mostly in yeast and bacterial species, as part of circular economy processes (Bertacchi et al., 2021, 2020; Leathers, 2003; Martins et al., 2021; Obruca et al., 2015). As an example, during the last years, there has been a rising number of studies exploring agro-industrial residues to produce polyhydroxyalkanoates using haloarchaea as biofactories (Alsafadi and Al-Mashaqbeh, 2017; Cai et al., 2021; Hermann-Krauss et al., 2013; Khamplod et al., 2023; Pramanik et al., 2012; Salgaonkar and Bragança, 2017; Wang and Zhang, 2021). Despite that, there is only one study exploring the effect on haloarchaeal cell cultures and carotenoid production (Will Chen et al., 2015). Chen and collaborators have assessed the use of extruded rice bran to grow *H. mediterranei* species (Will Chen et al., 2015), obtaining promising results in terms of carotenoid synthesis. However, further exploration is needed to understand the effect of different industrial residues on growth and carotenogenesis to optimize the protocol for a scale-up, thus promoting waste recycling. This work aims to study *H. mediterranei* growth and carotenoid production using wastes from the candy industry consisting of starch, thus contributing to the development of sustainable processes aiming at the production of natural pigments.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. *Haloflex mediterranei* R-4 (ATCC 33500) strain growth conditions

H. mediterranei strain R-4 (ATCC33500) was used for all experiments. Cells were grown in a complex medium (CM) containing 12.5 % (w/v) of

inorganic salts and 0.5 % (w/v) yeast extract (Condalab; Madrid, Spain). The additional carbon source employed is industrial waste from the candy industry consisting of starch in a concentration range of 0.5–2.5 % (w/v), which was directly (without any pretreatment) added to the culture media before autoclaving. 1/(w/v) D(+)-Glucose anhydrous BioChemica (Panreac AppliChem; Barcelona, Spain) and CM without additional carbon source were used as controls. The medium contains 12.5 % salt water (SW) with the next composition: 0.7 g NaBr, 0.2 g NaHCO₃, 6 g KCl, 41.5 g MgCl₂·6H₂O, 59.3 g de MgSO₄·7H₂O and 234 g NaCl. The pH was buffered using 30 mM Tris (Panreac AppliChem; Darmstadt, Germany) and was adjusted to a final pH 7.3 using HCl or NaOH. Cultures are incubated in an orbital shaking incubator (Infors HT Multitron Standard) at 170 rpm at 36.5 °C based on previous data (Giani et al., 2021a; Montero-Lobato et al., 2018). Cells were incubated until three days had passed after the maximum absorbance was reached (stationary phase of growth). Considering that BR is a secondary metabolite, it is mostly synthesized during the stationary phase. After that, cells were centrifuged at 7800 rpm for 30 min to remove the supernatant. Then, cells were washed twice with a 10 % (w/v) inorganic salts solution to remove cell culture remnants. Cell pellets were stored at –20 °C until carotenoid extraction was carried out.

Growth-specific velocity (1) and duplication time (2) were calculated for each growth condition using the following expressions:

$$\mu = \ln(X-X_0)/(t-t_0)(1)$$

$$Dt = \ln(2)/\mu(2)$$

2.2. Growth determination

Growth was determined by measuring the turbidity of the culture at 600 nm using an UV–Vis spectrophotometer (Agilent, Santa Clara, CA, USA). The correlation between OD₆₀₀ and cell number for *H. mediterranei* (Cells ml⁻¹ = OD600 * 9.69E8) was estimated using a cell staining protocol with SYBR green (Noble and Fuhrman, 1998; Torregrosa-Crespo et al., 2019).

2.3. Carotenoid extraction and BR quantification

Cell pellets were suspended in pure acetone of HPLC grade (Panreac AppliChem, Panreac Quimica, Barcelona, Spain) in a ratio of 1 ml of acetone per 10 ml of cell culture (Montero-Lobato et al., 2018). They were incubated at 4 °C overnight and then centrifuged (7800 rpm, 30 min) to obtain the carotenoid extract (supernatant). BR concentration was calculated using the following expression (Montero-Lobato et al., 2018):

$$\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} = (\text{OD}_{494}/2540) \times 10^4(3)$$

BR extracts were stored at –20 °C. Absorption UV–visible spectra were obtained at room temperature using a Cary 60 UV–Vis Spectrophotometer (Agilent, Santa Clara, CA, USA) using the scan mode, with a 300–800 nm absorbance range. Acetone was used as blank and baseline correction. Sample dilutions were made with acetone to avoid saturation of the spectrophotometric measurements of the extracts (1:10 dilution for 0.5 %, 1 % and 1.5 % (w/v) industrial starch; and 1:20 dilution for 2 % and 2.5 % (w/v) industrial starch). The spectra are represented with the dilution factor applied.

2.4. Determination of carotenoid composition by HPLC-MS

The HPLC analysis of carotenoids in acetone was performed using a Zorbax extended –C18 column (Agilent, Santa Clara, CA, USA) (2.1 × 50 mm, 1.8 μ m) on an Agilent 1200 series system (Santa Clara, CA, USA). To determine the mass spectra of the different compounds, a 6490 Triple Quad LC/MS system (Agilent, Santa Clara, CA, USA) was used

equipped with an electrospray ionization source (ESI) jet stream operating in positive scan mode (m/z range of 300–900) with 0.1 a.m.u (atomic mass unit) precision and controlled by MassHunter Workstation Software (Agilent, B.05.00, Santa Clara, CA, USA). The following specific working conditions were used: capillary voltage 3000 V, gas flow rate 11 L min⁻¹, gas temperature 290 °C, sheath gas flow rate 12 L min⁻¹, sheath gas temperature 300 °C, and nebulizer pressure 35 psi. The percentage represented by each carotenoid was calculated by dividing the sum of the areas of a carotenoid by the sum of the areas of all identified carotenoids.

2.5. Statistical analysis

Data are expressed as the mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Statistical significance was calculated by ANOVA (followed by Dunnett's test for multiple comparisons) analysis using GraphPad 8 software (GraphPad Software; Dotmatics; San Diego, California, USA). The differences were considered statistically significant at p -values $< 0.05^*$, $< 0.01^{**}$, $< 0.001^{***}$, $< 0.0001^{****}$. All experiments were repeated at least three times unless otherwise indicated.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Cultures growth

Haloflex mediterranei grew successfully in the presence of the starch residue from the candy industry (Fig. 1). The pH of the cell culture remained constant under all starch concentrations assayed. In all tested concentrations, cells grew better than the control without any additional carbon source (Fig. 1), coinciding with previous results (Giani et al., 2022). In all cases but the lowest concentration (0.5 % (w/v), the detected absorbances were higher than cells growing with 1 % glucose (w/v). Earlier experiments using soluble starch led to similar results to those obtained for the same concentrations of glucose (Giani et al., 2022). However, in this study, the use of starch residues from the candy industry led to higher absorbance values than those reported for the use of glucose and soluble starch of chemical quality. Therefore, this industrial waste could successfully be used for the cultivation of *H. mediterranei*. Diauxic growth was observed in cell cultures containing from 1 % to 2.5 % starch. First, the exponential phase was very steep followed by a much more controlled growth in the following hours.

Fig. 1. Effect of different concentrations of starch residues from the candy industry (0.5–2.5 % (w/v)) on the time course of growth (OD₆₀₀ nm (mean \pm SD)) of *H. mediterranei*. Control without additional carbon source and cells growing in the presence of 1 % glucose (w/v) are also represented to facilitate comparison (n = 3 for each group).

Nevertheless, growth was far from impaired.

A concentration-dependent tendency was observed in the maximum absorbance values at 600 nm (Fig. 2). Maximum absorbances of those cell cultures containing starch reached values from 11.48 ± 0.08 to 27.75 ± 0.09 , as a result of both growth and pigment production, which are much higher than the maximum value reported in an optimization process in natural brine medium for *Halorubrum* sp. HRM-150 (highest OD₆₀₀ (3.21 ± 0.01) obtained after 96 h) (Ma et al., 2023). These results agree with previous results that demonstrated that starch could be metabolized by *H. mediterranei* (Will Chen et al., 2015). Other studies have explored the use of alternative nutrient sources for *H. mediterranei*, such as olive mill wastewater (Alsafadi and Al-Mashaqbeh, 2017). However, although no inhibitory effect at the lowest concentrations was observed, neither induction of cell growth as presented in this work.

3.2. Growth rate (μ)

All μ values obtained were significantly different ($p < 0.0001$) from both the control without an additional carbon source and the cell culture with 1 % glucose as a carbon source. Starch cell cultures grew faster than the controls during the first exponential phase. However, those which presented diauxic growth (1 %-2.5 %), showed μ values between 0.006–0.01 h⁻¹ during the second exponential phase. Previous studies using alternative nutrient sources have reported variable growth rates. The use of pure volatile fatty acids, crude glycerol phase from biodiesel production or hydrolysed rapeseed meal led to *H. mediterranei* μ values of 0.024 ± 0.0007 h⁻¹, 0.06 h⁻¹ and 0.028 – 0.064 ± 0.002 h⁻¹, respectively (Hermann-Krauss et al., 2013; Khamplod et al., 2023; Wang and Zhang, 2021). Another haloarchaeal species, *Halogeometricum borinquense* strain E3, showed a maximum μ value of 0.023 h⁻¹ in the presence of sugarcane bagasse (Salgaonkar and Bragança, 2017). Discrepancies between studies can be related to the growth behaviour (normal vs. diauxic) and equipment variability. Despite that, in this study, *H. mediterranei* showed significantly superior μ values highlighting the benefits of the use of this carbon-rich waste.

Biomass production increased in the presence of higher quantities of starch leading to a maximum value of 17.3 ± 0.2 mg/ml of cell culture (Fig. 3), which is a superior value to those previously reported in the literature. Previous work reported 5.414–11.085 mg/ml of *H. mediterranei* cell dry weight when grown in the presence of different

Fig. 2. Maximum absorbance (mean \pm SD) of cell cultures containing no additional carbon source (C), 1 % glucose (w/v) (G) and 0.5–2.5 % (w/v) starch residue from candy industry (S). All maximum absorbance values obtained in the starch cell cultures were significantly different ($p < 0.0001$) from both the control without an additional carbon source and the cell culture with 1 % glucose as a carbon source (n = 3 for each group).

Fig. 3. Biomass (mg/ml) (mean \pm SD) of cell cultures containing no additional carbon source (C), 1 % glucose (w/v) (G) and 0.5–2.5 % (w/v) starch residue from candy industry (S) ($n = 3$ for each group). *** $p < 0.001$, **** $p < 0.0001$.

concentrations of hydrolysed rapeseed meal (Khamplod et al., 2023). Another study presented an optimization process using a natural brine medium for *Halorubrum* sp. HRM-150 and reported a biomass of 10.4 mg/ml at 96 h (Ma et al., 2023).

3.3. Carotenoid production

Carotenoid production showed a concentration-dependent tendency with the concentration of starch added to the culture media. The concentration of BR reached was significantly higher than the controls with 1 % glucose and no additional carbon source. The maximum BR concentration was obtained from the extracts from cells grown in the presence of 2.5 % (w/v) industrial starch ($97.39 \pm 1.86 \mu\text{g/ml}$ BR), which was higher than recently reported for soluble starch ($90.83 \pm 1.31 \mu\text{g/ml}$ BR) (Giani et al., 2022). The rise in carbon source concentration has a dual effect: it promotes growth and triggers carotenoid synthesis, as carbon forms the fundamental building blocks of carotenoid molecules, coinciding with previous results (Giani et al., 2022). Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 demonstrate that carotenoid extracts from cell cultures with higher carbon availability exhibited elevated BR concentrations.

Even though in the bibliography numerous methods and units of

Fig. 4. BR concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) (mean \pm SD) of carotenoid extracts obtained from *H. mediterranei* cell cultures containing no additional carbon source (C), 1 % glucose (w/v) (G) and 0.5–2.5 % (w/v) starch residue from candy industry (S) ($n = 3$ for each group). **** $p < 0.0001$.

Fig. 5. UV-Vis Spectra (350–600 nm) of carotenoid extracts from *H. mediterranei* growth with 0.5–2.5 % (w/v) starch residue from the candy industry (S) ($n = 3$ for each group).

measurement can be found, the synergistic effect of low salt content and abundant carbon availability has resulted in the most efficient production of C₅₀ carotenoids (Giani et al., 2022). Our outcome surpasses most reported results in the literature (Abbes et al., 2013; Cerletti et al., 2018; Flores et al., 2020; Kumar and Chauhan, 2021; Ma et al., 2023; Montero-Lobato et al., 2018; Naziri et al., 2014; Vázquez-Madrugal et al., 2021) except a study (Will Chen et al., 2015), where a maximum of 556 mg/L of total carotenoids was attained under conditions of high salt concentration. The discrepancy in BR production between most studies and Chen and collaborators might be attributed to the maintenance of constant conductivity and/or variations in the formula used to calculate the concentration of BR.

The UV-visible spectrum showed the characteristic peaks of BR at 368, 386, 463, 494 and 530 nm (Fig. 5). It is worth highlighting that the extract obtained displayed a significant increase in absorbance at 388 nm, possibly suggesting a higher abundance of *cis*-BR-isomers (Flores et al., 2020; Mandelli et al., 2012). Carotenoid extracts obtained from *H. mediterranei* cells grown in the presence of soluble starch did not show high values at 388 nm (Giani et al., 2022). One possible explanation is that this starch residue from the candy industry since it is not pure, has other components or contaminants which might be altering the synthesis of BR isomers.

Our findings continue to reinforce the idea that an excess of carbon, along with low salinity (12.5 %) and low temperature (36.5 °C) conditions, provide *H. mediterranei* with the essential resources to enhance the synthesis of BR, enabling it to better cope with osmotic stress. The use of a low-cost carbon source, such as the one presented in this article, contributes to the optimisation process for a further scale-up by reducing production costs.

3.4. Determination of carotenoid composition by HPLC-MS

The carotenoid extracts obtained from cell cultures supplemented with 0.5–2.5 % (w/v) starch residue underwent HPLC-MS analysis to determine their composition. The total carotenoid content was estimated from the total area values obtained from the HPLC-MS. These values confirm the increasing levels of carotenoids in the extracts (Supplementary Materials: S1), thus indicating that carotenogenesis was induced in the presence of increasing amounts of this carbon source. The m/z value (740.6) corresponding to BR was detected at multiple retention times during the elution, spanning from 3 to 8 min. These findings indicated the presence of various BR isomers. In Fig. 6, it is evident that the total amount of bacterioruberins (excluding different isomers) showed a slight increase in a positive correlation with the concentration

Fig. 6. Percentage of total BR (mean \pm SD) about the total of carotenoids identified in each sample ($n = 3$ for each group). Each experimental sample was compared to the control to evaluate statistical significance. * $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$, **** $p < 0.0001$.

of the carbon source in the culture media from which they were derived. BR constituted approximately 72 % to 86 % of the identified carotenoids, aligning with previous results highlighting BR as the principal component of haloarchaeal carotenoid extracts (Asker et al., 2002; Fang et al., 2010; Flores et al., 2020; Hou and Cui, 2018; Ronnekleiv, 1995), and showing higher values than those reported for commercial soluble starch (68 % to 81 %) (Giani et al., 2022).

Limited information exists concerning the identification of BR isomers. In our carotenoid extracts, BR eluted within the range of 3 to 8 min, closely aligning with our previous results and those reported by Lizama and collaborators (Giani et al., 2022; Lizama et al., 2021). We observed five distinct retention time zones where BR was identified (Giani et al., 2022) which correspond to the following isomers: all-*trans*-BR, 5-*cis*-BR, 9-*cis*-BR, 13-*cis*-BR and a double isomeric form (Flores et al., 2020; Giani et al., 2022; Lizama et al., 2021). After identifying the various isomers based on their retention times, we proceeded to calculate the percentage that each of them represented concerning the total carotenoids (Supplementary Materials: S2). The all-*trans*-BR isomer proved to be the most abundant, comprising approximately 32.5 % to 40.1 % of the total carotenoid content, which closely aligns with previous findings (Flores et al., 2020; Giani et al., 2022) (Supplementary Materials: S2A). However, its abundance was somewhat lower than what was reported by Mandelli and collaborators.

The internal control, extracted from a cell culture without any supplementary carbon source, showed only the presence of all-*trans*-BR and 9-*cis*-BR isomers, coinciding with the results obtained for soluble starch (Giani et al., 2022) (Supplementary Materials: S2A-E). However, in the other extracts obtained from cells exposed to higher starch residue concentrations, a diverse mix of isomers was identified, including all-*trans*-BR, 5-*cis*-BR, 9-*cis*-BR, 13-*cis*-BR, and at least one double isomeric BR form (Supplementary Materials: S2A-E). The percentages of 5-*cis*-BR, 9-*cis*-BR, and 13-*cis*-BR in these extracts varied from 11.0 % to 15.9 %, 4.5 % to 10.0 %, and 4.8 % to 9.8 %, respectively, which is consistent with previous research (Flores et al., 2020). The double isomeric form was present in percentages ranging between 8.7–20.8 %.

Thus, as recently reported by our research group, the nutritional conditions significantly impact the production of BR isomers in *H. mediterranei* (Giani et al., 2022). Specifically, higher carbon concentrations resulted in increased percentages of all-*trans*-BR, 5-*cis*-BR, and the double isomeric BR form, while reducing the presence of 9-*cis*-BR and 13-*cis*-BR. This trend was consistent with the results obtained last year for extracts obtained from both glucose- and soluble starch-supplemented cell cultures, confirming that it is primarily influenced

by the carbon source's concentration rather than its type (Giani et al., 2022). It is essential to emphasize that the percentages of the double isomeric form are notably higher compared to extracts from cells grown with glucose or soluble starch. This difference justifies the higher absorbance values observed at 388 nm in the UV-Vis spectra shown in Fig. 5. In contrast to our findings in *H. mediterranei* (present results and our previous study (Giani et al., 2022)), a previous study on *Halococcus morrhuae* and *Halobacterium salinarium* reported that 13-*cis*-BR was more abundant than 9-*cis*-BR and 5-*cis*-BR in their carotenoid extracts (Mandelli et al., 2012).

In the carotenoid extracts, we detected the presence of mono-anhydrobacterioruberin (MABR; $m/z = 722$), trisanhydrobacterioruberin (TRISABR; $m/z = 686$) and tetraanhydrobacterioruberin (TETRABR; $m/z = 668$) in concentrations ranging from 3.8 % to 5.1 %, 5.6 % to 17.1 %, and 1.1 % to 5.6 %, respectively (Supplementary Materials: S3). Interestingly, MABR abundance showed a slight increase in extracts from high-carbon-availability cell cultures as reported previously (Giani et al., 2022) while BABR ($m/z = 704$) was detected in some of the extracts but not all of them, and in percentages below 1 %, which differs from the results obtained using soluble starch. On the contrary, there is a greater abundance of TRISABR and TETRABR compared to soluble starch, although their percentages decrease with higher carbon availability. Xanthophylls were present in all extracts except the control without any additional carbon source. Specifically, the percentage of canthaxanthin decreased with higher carbon availability in the culture media, ranging between 0.03–0.1 % of the total carotenoids. Therefore, it exhibited an inverse correlation with the concentration of carbon in the culture media. Astaxanthin was also detected in some samples without a concentration-dependent tendency and in percentages below 0.04 % of the total identified carotenoids. Previous studies have also reported the synthesis of xanthophylls in halophilic microorganisms (Asker et al., 2002; Asker and Ohta, 1999; Squillaci et al., 2017).

Agro-industrial residues have been extensively explored as potential substrates for bioplastic production in haloarchaea, with numerous studies investigating their utilization for this purpose (Alsafadi and Al-Mashaqbeh, 2017; Cai et al., 2021; Hermann-Krauss et al., 2013; Khamplod et al., 2023; Pramanik et al., 2012; Salgaonkar and Bragança, 2017; Wang and Zhang, 2021). However, despite the growing interest in haloarchaeal carotenoids due to their potential biomedical and biotechnological applications, the research landscape for carotenoid production remains relatively limited. Apart from this present work, which sheds light on the use of starch residues to enhance carotenoid production in *Haloferax mediterranei*, only one other study has used another industrial residue with a specific focus on carotenoid synthesis in haloarchaea (Will Chen et al., 2015). This indicates a significant gap in the understanding of the full potential of these microorganisms as carotenoid producers, despite the evident advantages they offer in terms of sustainable and cost-effective production methods. Consequently, there is a promising opportunity for further exploration and investigation to fully unravel the untapped potential of haloarchaea in the realm of carotenoid biosynthesis, potentially unlocking new avenues for their industrial applications in various sectors.

4. Conclusion

This study represents a significant step forward in the quest for sustainable and cost-effective carotenoid production by harnessing the potential of utilizing industrial waste products, specifically starch residues from the candy industry, to promote haloarchaeal growth and enhance carotenoid synthesis. Moreover, the considerable increase in biomass production observed in the presence of higher concentrations of starch highlights the viability of this approach for achieving higher yields of carotenoids. The substantial concentration of bacterioruberin (BR) obtained, along with its composition variations in response to different starch concentrations, further validates the efficiency of this

strategy in modulating carotenoid profiles for specific applications.

Overall, the successful utilization of industrial starch residues from the candy industry as a substrate for carotenoid production in this study showcases the remarkable adaptability and resourcefulness of haloarchaea, while also offering a compelling solution for a more sustainable and economically viable route to obtain these valuable molecules. As research in this area progresses, further optimization of the process and exploration of other waste streams will undoubtedly unlock even greater potential for carotenoid production, shaping a more environmentally friendly and economically prosperous future for industries reliant on these precious compounds.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Author's contributions

M.G. carried out the experiments, data analysis and interpretation, and contributed to the writing of the final draft. C.P. contributed to writing the final draft and editing. R.M.M.E. was involved in conceptualization, project administration, supervision, and revising the final draft. All authors contributed to the writing and the final revision. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Data availability.

The datasets analysed during the current study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crbiot.2024.100265>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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